

A Novel Surveillance System for Passenger Safety and Monitoring the Driver Behavior through Vehicular Ad hoc Network

Dr.M. Jaganathan¹, Ms.K. Sneka²

¹Assistant Professor PG and Research Department of Computer Science
Kaamadhenu Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Sathyamangalam

²Assistant Professor PG and Research Department of Computer Science
Kaamadhenu Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Sathyamangalam

Abstract - The system comprises of two Electronic Control Units (ECU) - Active Vehicle Control (AVC) to measure the driver's driving behavior and Passenger Safety Control (PSC) for ensuring the safety during travelling in private vehicles. The AVC module is a Global System for Mobile (GSM) based ECU which consists of multiple sensor that measures the driver's abnormal or race driving behavior and correspondingly report to the call taxi company through GSM. The PSC module enables the passenger to stop the vehicle by pressing the emergency stop button. The Vehicular Ad-Hoc Network (VANET) also known as Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) communication shares the real time traffic related information between the vehicles to reach the destination on time thereby avoiding accidents and traffic congestion. The proposed system is found to be superior to ensure security for passengers than traditional approaches.

Keywords: AVC, ECU, GSM, Novel Surveillance System, PSC, VANET.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Today's world of an increasing population, public transport remains the primary mode of transport for most of the population but there is problem in reaching the destination on time. Nowadays most of the people such as employees, business persons, school and college students, etc., are mostly using the taxi for the transportations. So many private companies provide the taxi services to public. Large metropolitan areas offer an alternative transport of taxis services in that they often provide mass transit systems such as buses and subways. As these mass transit systems are designed to move large numbers of people efficiently, they do not provide privacy for their occupants[1]. However the security is the main concerns in taxi transportation since business persons and ladies are sometimes travelled alone in Taxi. Especially more concerns on ladies using the taxi services in night times. In recent times the taxi services are misused for criminal activities such as kidnaps and murders. Therefore for the above reason, the need arises to provide the secure travelling to the passengers by providing the emergency stop control system which stops the vehicle without aid of driver. Along to the passenger safety the driver's driving behavior need to be analyzed because the drivers are becoming more important to vehicle control, safety and performance.

Jianqiang Wang et al. [2] suggested a Forward Collision Warning (FCW) Algorithm with Adaptation to Driver Behaviours that can adjust its warning thresholds in a real-time manner according to driver behavior changes, including both behavioural fluctuation and individual difference. This adaptive FCW algorithm overcomes the limit of traditional FCW with fixed risk evaluation models and fixed triggering thresholds by continuously monitoring driver braking behaviors in multiple lanes.

Yi Han, Yuan Yao and Haiyang Liu[3] represented the design and implementation of Driving Behaviour Analysis System that depicts the characteristics of driving behaviour and improves the road safety. This system could acquire and analyse drivers' driving behaviour needed. The hardware system is made up of two computers. The software system includes Speed Dreams engine, the Monitor program and the Data Analysis program.

Jiangpeng Dai, Jin Teng, Xiaole Bai, Zhaohui Shen and Dong Xuan [4] proposed mobile phone based drunk driving detection system. This system places the mobile phone in the vehicle, collects and analyses the data from its accelerometer and orientation sensor to detect any abnormal or dangerous driving manoeuvres typically related to driving under alcohol influence.

Mamidi Kiran Kumar, V. Kamakshi Prasad [5] discussed their survey on driver behavior analysis and prediction models. Their survey revealed the fact that a more precise definition of driver behavior analysis models would focus on various methods to understand the driver behavior, and also give information regarding driver driving information. The driver behavior prediction models give predictions of the drivers' driving nature whether the driving is safe or not.

Joel C. McCall and Mohan M. Trivedi [6] proposed a work on driver behavior and situation aware brake assistance for Intelligent Vehicles. This is a novel method for fusing predicted driver behavioral information with vehicle and surround information for braking assistance. The framework allows for the assessment of the criticality of the current situation and the need for intervention by an intelligent vehicle safety system.

Scott Schnelle and Junmin Wang [7] presented a sensitivity analysis of a human driver model under various road and driving conditions. A systematic simulation study conducted revealed how the vehicle y-position tracking error is related to the driver steering characteristics under various operating and road conditions in common maneuvers.

Thus Driving style has various impacts on hazardous driving behavior detection and fuel economy. Driving style differ among drivers. Drivers who are less prone to sudden maneuvers will have a lower possibility of suffering a dangerous situation thus fuel consumption will also decrease. Hence driver's driving conditions need to be analyzed for warning the drivers if there are any of the abnormal driving condition detected.

The Novel Surveillance System denotes monitoring and observing the behavior or activity analysis of vehicle driving condition and implementation of passenger safety in private vehicles such as call taxi and tourist travelers. The main focus of this study is to provide a secure travel to the passengers by providing the emergency stop control system which stops the vehicle without the aid of the driver.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Existing Method

Some of the existing studies reveals the fact that, Naturalistic Driving Studies (NDS) captures large volumes of drive data from multiple sensor modalities which are analyzed for critical information about driver behavior and driving characteristics. Also, NDS data usually contain video-recordings of the driver and the traffic environment, as well as a large number of time-history measurements (e.g., speed, acceleration, operational responses). A similar data collection approach is used for evaluations of advanced driver safety system (ADAS). But, this method is a data base method. The driving behavior is measured and stored in the database then it will be analyzed on frequent base. It does not immediately report on real time.

The next existing method is Personalized Driver Model established for evaluating the driving style for each driver. The personalized driver model using the real world vehicle test condition and locally designed neural network. The method is designed and implemented in the Drive Assist System after evaluating the driver's real environment driving condition for some period of time.

The above mentioned studies does not report the taxi driver's driving behavior such as abnormal driving and unsafe driving behaviors on time.

B. Proposed System

The Novel Surveillance System in this work will act as a digital interface utilized on various applications by providing security and protection in transportation. This system will be housed on a single microprocessor board; virtually all appliances that have a digital interface utilize this system. In addition to that, the application can also be extended for vehicle safety measures to examine the vehicle behavior, monitor the vehicular speed and driver's behavior. A centralized system will collect and analyze all the information from various sources and takes the appropriate decision. The overview of the system proposed is given in the Fig. 1.

The system as shown in Figure 1 consists of three sections such as Input unit, Control unit and Output unit. The Input unit consists of multiple sensors which continuously measure their corresponding parameters then it feed to the control unit. The Control unit constructed by microcontroller is programmed as per the requirement. It received the measured raw data from the sensor unit then compared with programmed set value and based on the result it controls the corresponding output unit. The output unit consists of LCD, warning lights, vehicle speed control and GSM module. Further, the system comprises of Active Vehicle Control module (AVC) which measures the driver's driving behavior and Passenger Safety Control module (PSC) for ensuring the safety during travelling in private vehicles

Fig. 1: Overview of the System

A. AVC Module: The Active Vehicle Control module is a GSM based ECU which constitutes multiple sensors that measure the driver's abnormal driving behavior and correspondingly report to the call taxi company through GSM.

The Active Vehicle Control ECU consists of

(i). The Speed measurement sensor to measure the speed and give the warning of over speed. The Speed measurement method is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Speed Measurement

(ii). A hi-sensitivity alcohol sensor is built into the transmission shift knob, to detect the presence of alcohol in the perspiration of the driver's palm as he or she attempts to start driving. Alcohol level sensing method is shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3: Alcohol level Measurement

(iii). Eye blink sensor gives the alert signal, driver's drowsiness

Fig.4: Eye blinking level Measurement

and driver's attention warning of unsafe driving. Eye blinking level sensing method is shown in Fig 4.

(iv) GSM module which sends driver behavior report to Call Taxi owner or company. GSM module interfacing method is shown in Fig 5.

Fig. 5: GSM module interface

B. PSC Module

When passenger suspects the driver behavior or character is wrong while travelling time or suspect that driver going on wrong route, the passenger can stop the vehicle by pressing the emergency stop button which is placed in the rear seat roof.

Now the ECU detects emergency stop instruction and it is automatically reduce the vehicle speed and stop the vehicle. Simultaneously flashing the Emergency stop warning light on rear side to indicate other vehicle that is the vehicle is going to stop. It also unlocks the all doors so the passenger can come out of the vehicle. The PSC ESC module is shown in Fig 6.

Fig. 6: PSC ECU

The PSC ECU consists of

- (i) Emergency STOP button which is placed in the rear seat roof.
- (ii) Emergency STOP warning light which is placed on the rear end.
- (iii) Automatic speed reduction and stop control unit.

C. VANET Module

The Vehicular Ad hoc Network also known as Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) communication shares the real time traffic related information between the vehicles to reach the destination on time. They can be effective in avoiding accidents and traffic congestion. The VANET module is shown in Fig 7.

The VANET module is shown in Fig 7.

Fig. 7: VANET

System Level Architecture

The System level architecture describes the hierarchy level of operation which is shown in below Fig. 8. The lowest level is the data layer constructed by hardware unit such as sensors and signaling and conditioning circuit.

This data layer section measures the driving behavior such as speed and other parameters. The next hierarchy level is the control layer which is constructed by both software and hardware unit. The measured parameters in the data layers are monitored and controlled through the controller layer.

Fig. 8: System Level Architecture

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment has been conducted as a bench level test to ensure the efficiency of the proposed system. The experiment shown in the Fig. 9 consists of The Proposed Novel Surveillance System two ECUs constructed with multiple sensors to measure the driving behavior condition. The sensed signals are sent to the PIC Microcontroller. If there any abnormality detected in the driving, it will warn the driver using some warning indicators and same warning information is sent as SMS to the vehicle owners through the GSM module.

FIG. 9: ECU HARDWARE SETUP

The proposed Novel Surveillance System includes the above hardware setup and is found to be superior to its ancestor systems. The vehicle speed measurement, detection of drunk and drive, drowsiness driving concluded the abnormal driving behavior. Emergency stop control system stopped the vehicle without the aid of driver. The real time traffic related information was shared between vehicles through V2V communication network.

IV. CONCLUSION

Road environment, vehicles and road users are all part of the road transport system. Among them, the human factor is the most complex and dynamic. Whether the road users follow traffic rules and adopt a careful and considerate driving attitude has a great bearing on road safety. The simplicity and robustness of this model makes ideal for driver behavior sensing for safer and better driving environment. This is especially designed for the rented vehicle where the driver does not care about the vehicle condition and doing some rash driving which cause the passenger to feel unpleasant as well as the unsafe travelling. Moreover the rash driving of sudden acceleration and deceleration also decrease the fuel economy. The Active Vehicle Control ECU is designed to measure such an abnormal driving behavior and it is not only gives warning to the driver it will also send an abnormal driving status to the vehicle owner. Along with the Intelligent Passenger Safety ECU enables the passengers especially ladies to have safe travelling even during night times. In the near future, these two ECUs can be implemented in the Drive Assist System to enhance vehicle systems for safety and better driving.

REFERENCES

1. World-Health-Organization, Global status report on road safety: time for action. 2009, World Health Organization: Geneva.
2. Jianqiang Wang et al, "A Forward Collision Warning Algorithm with Adaptation to Driver Behaviours", IEEE Transactions, 2015.
3. Yi Han, Yuan Yao, and Haiyang Liu, "Design and Implementation of Driving Behavior Analysis System", journal of networks, vol. 9, no. 8, august 2014.
4. Jiangpeng Dai, Jin Teng, Xiaole Bai, Zhaohui Shen and Dong Xuan, "Mobile Phone Based Drunk Driving Detection", <http://dx.doi.org/10.4108//CST.PERVASIVEHEALTH2010.890>.
5. Mamidi Kiran Kumar, V. Kamakshi Prasad, "Driver Behavior Analysis and Prediction Models: A Survey", International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, Vol. 6 (4), 2015, 3328-3333.
6. Joel C. McCall and Mohan M. Trivedi, "Driver Behavior and Situation Aware Brake Assistance for Intelligent Vehicles", Proceedings of the IEEE | Vol. 95, No. 2, February 2007.
7. Scott Schnelle and Junmin Wang, "Sensitivity Analysis of Human Driving Characteristics on Road and Driving Conditions for Active Vehicle Control Systems", IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics October 5-8, 2014, San Diego, CA, USA.